

PUBLIC POLICY AND MANAGEMENT- A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract:

Public Policy and Management is a timely topic for discussion, as it affects all of us and so we should try to know about it thoroughly. Public Policy formulation has been there since the beginning of civilization. But with the publication of the book "Policy Sciences" by Harold Lasswell and Daniel Lerner, it has gained a new orientation. Though public policy has been formulated and implemented all over the world, we limit our discussion to its status in India. We also discuss its connection to the Management science. Public Policy is a Government Policy and not a private one. It is a policy matter of life and death of people as it determines the quality of their lives. Public Policy is concerned with the governance of governments and good governments adopt good policies in order to make people happy and healthy. India is a democratic state. It has a constitution which guarantees freedom, security and happiness to its people. Its Fundamental rights and Directive Principles of State Policy support these ideals. In our country policy formulation is done at the central, state and local levels. Except for a few departments like Defense, Finance and Foreign policies all other policies are handled by the state governments at the District and block levels using thousands of workers catering to the needs of millions of people. Agencies like the Planning Commission now replaced by NITI - Aayog, National Defense Commission, National Finance Commission and Inter-State Councils, Coordinate policy making between the Center and the States. In addition to the Government, Political Parties, Social Organization's NGO's, Scholars and Experts in certain fields take part in policy making. Many social organizations have now started demanding service from the government through policy implementation. For proper policy implementation, we have to take recourse to the principles of Management. By defining the roles and team building principles by setting targets and adopting scientific methods, by encouraging innovations and by seeking feedback from the beneficiaries, It is possible to satisfactorily implement the policies. Proper evaluation also is important in policy implementation. Statistical methods and third party evaluation are very helpful. Globalization has affected all of us. By managing the Global pressures, we should continue serving the interests of Indian citizens. Of course this will be a Hard Challenge for the Indian Policy Makers. They can meet these Challenges if they adopt intelligently and painstakingly the principles of Public Management

Key Words: Public Policy, Planning Commission, NITI-Aayog, E-Governance, Bureaucracy

Public Policy and Management - A Conceptual Framework:

Public Policy & Management is a topic very relevant and timely as it affects all of us one way or other. We know how the policy of Demonetization has come into force shattering the dreams of many of us and inconveniencing all of us. Public policy is the Policy or an agreed plan of action of the Government and the public at large. It is not the private policy of a person affecting one or two people but it pertains to all the people and its implications are very far reaching. Prabir Kumar De in his book "Public Policy and Systems" defines Public Policy as an area of Government activity in which broader interests of the Public are linked and such areas may be education, health, housing, agriculture and so on. Even the foreign policy is referred to as the public policy of a Nation. Therefore it can be stated that any Government activity of wider ramifications for the people is considered a public policy. It is the allocation of values for the whole society by the Government by taking the public interest into consideration. The Government needs a policy to impress the people by giving concrete shape to its political, economic and social objectives. In its various fields of administration like Education, Defense, Health and Finance, it formulates policies known as public policies. A Government is known by its policies and the state will be an ideal welfare state if its policies are progressive, pragmatic and egalitarian.

Our India is a welfare State, a democratic, sovereign republic and it has a constitution reflecting the aspirations and dreams of all its people. The Preamble of the Constitution contains many provisions supporting the basic political values, Democracy, Justice, Liberty, Equality, Fraternity, Socialism and Secularism. Part 3 of the constitution contains the Fundamental Rights and Part 4 the Directive Principles of State Policy, whose aim is to promote social, economic and institutional changes for building a welfare state and society. All these are necessary for good governance and so a good government should formulate a number of public policies and see

that they are properly implemented. Viewed in this context, the topic of Public Policy and Management makes perfect sense.

It is our belief that long long ago in Tretayuga there lived a perfect king who made possible a Ramarajya or a Utopian state. It was Lord Sri Rama who accomplished this gigantic task by sincerely implementing ideal public policies. So it is clear that the formulation and implementation of public policy has been in existence from times immemorial. And now public policy is being formulated in a more precise manner and is now seen in different shades and avatars. But it is not to be forgotten that the aim is nobler and for the larger public good and happiness.

Now public policy has carved a niche for itself. It has been made a part and parcel of the Policy sciences. This takes us back to 1951 when Harold Lasswell and Daniel Lerner published their monumental work "Policy Sciences". That work is the first systematic effort towards a new field of enquiry to deal with social problems. Though public policy formulation had been in practice earlier, it is the first theorization of the practice of public policy. Before that Public Policy was considered a part of Political Science and Public Administration. Harold Lasswell called his book "Policy Sciences" as the public policy is multidisciplinary, contextual, problem oriented and normative in nature. The World Development Report of 2015 finds that besides Social Sciences, subjects like Neurosciences, Cognitive Sciences, Psychology and Behavioral Economics to be very useful in policy formulation. That is why R.K. Saprú says that unity of knowledge is the prominent theme in Policy Sciences.

India has a federal form of Government and so the public policy shapes at three different levels. At the union level the policies are framed by the Central government with regard to the Central subjects. The Government personnel are not supposed to know everything. There are several fields of development and there are some experienced people called experts in every field. The Government depends on these experts for policy making. The expert committees appointed by the Prime Minister and Ministers give appropriate advice to the Government. The advice if accepted will become the policy of the Government and this is how a policy is born and it will be formulated appropriately for implementation in the entire country. At the state level policies are framed in state subjects. At the local panchayat level policies are framed in the permitted areas. Agencies like the Planning Commission now replaced by NITI-Aayog, National Development Commission, National Finance Commission and Interstate Council coordinate policy making between the centre and the states. The Prime Minister and his Cabinet at the Centre, the Chief Minister and his Cabinet in the states enact laws and pass resolutions which have policy implications.

Old India is disappearing and a rich new India is emerging flooded by mobiles, WIFI connectivity and other technological gadgets. These gadgets are now used by the social media to mobilize flash mobs as done during the Nirbhaya protests and the Lokpal movement. Nirbhaya a 23 year old Paramedical student was gang raped by 6 men in a private bus and thrown out of the moving bus along with her male friend. This case which happened in 2012 gained momentum only after a concerted campaign by the Women's rights Organisations and other sympathizers. The Lokpal movement also began similarly. It is a movement called "India against corruption". The saintly and honest Anna Hazare, Arvind Kejriwal and Kiran Bedi led the masses who championed the movement. They wanted the enactment of JAN Lokpal Bill to eradicate corruption. After a number of demonstrations, protests and mass gatherings at Janter-Mandir, New Delhi, the Lokpal Bill was passed in 2013. In all these cases, the policies were initiated by the Public who in turn persuaded the Government to enact them as public policies.

This trend is changing the idea and practice of Public Policy. The Government also has become ready to encourage private initiative. Owing to the paradigm shift in society, civil society organizations have gained far greater public faith than the Political Parties, MPs and MLAs. These groups now could mobilize people at the grassroots for mass agitation in support of their movements such as right to information movement, anti-child labour movement and the right to food movement. People are now giving up agitating for religious and caste reasons and started demanding a share in policy making. They are also asking the government to perform its basic duties of governance and service delivery.

A Public Policy remains a policy statement unless and until it is implemented and here comes the Science of public management to play its role. Management experts know the specific functions necessary to the organization and implementation of public policy. Being experts in planning, organizing, directing and controlling the projects, the public managers are skilled in the implementation of any policy. To quote R.K. Saprú again "Public Policy and Public Management are partners, convergent in outcome, yet with different outlooks". L. Lynn in his book "Managing Public Policy" says that "Managing Public Policy" is the result of executive effort directed at affecting governmental outcomes by influencing the processes, which design and carry out governmental activity".

It is said that in India the formulation of policies is all right, but they are not properly implemented. So it is necessary to improve the method of implementation and for this we have to find out the factors that make for poor implementation. It will be helpful if NGOs, beneficiaries and stakeholders join hands with the Government, sit together and discuss ways and means of proper implementation. The field of implementation

also is changing fast with the quick adoption of the IT technology and the Internet. E governance is seen to be a game changer for public service delivery. The use of Information and Communication Technology or ICT will facilitate the Digital Governance or e – Governance leading to a more transparent and effective democratic governance. In the words of Dr. Harpreeth Kaur “e- Governance has actually given an opportunity of paradigm shift in the process of delivery of government services to the Public”. The following are the goals of e Governance.

- ✓ It's a tool to help better service delivery to citizens and plays a good role in any poverty alleviation strategy.
- ✓ It extends improved services to many domestic and international businesses.
- ✓ E- Governance leads to transparency and helps anti corruption initiatives.
- ✓ It also empowers the poor and underprivileged through the supply of information which can be used to make the Government accountable.

Let us now look at the implementation mechanism in our country. The executive has to implement the policies. But the services do not have sufficient man power. There are no sufficient numbers of employees to run the entire show. Adding to this shortage of workforce is the fact that the available staffs do not have relevant skills. Even the individual available staffs are discouraged from playing their roles owing to lack of incentives. Many of them are corrupt and in spite of the CBI and other anti corruption agencies, we are not in a position to weed out corruption. Excepting a few union subjects like Finance, Foreign Affairs and defense, most matters of Public Policy are implemented at the state level through the Ministerial Department and by the District and Block level officers. They in turn involve a network of Government employees like the school teachers, departmental personnel or a group of special recruits. Thus delivering a development program to people is a gigantic task for a national program, as it involves thousands of workers and a clientele of tens of millions. So Policy implementation is a hard challenge. Here a few useful Broad Management Principles are quoted from Rajesh Chakrabarty's Book, “Public Policy in India”.

- ✓ **Setting Clear Time Bound Quantitative Targets:** The implementation of a good policy should have a clear time bound target. It is the basic for any project management and is an indicator of success. Mr. Sridharan, boss of Delhi Metro used this method successfully and achieved amazing results. He converted the continuing project into a Mission project by setting periodic targets and achieved zero backlog by a specified date.
- ✓ **Clarity of Roles and Team Building Principles:** Every employee of the project should know clearly what he should do and how he should complete it in cooperation with other members of his team. Policy work will be generally spread over large areas and so large teams of workers are necessary. Here role clarity and specified responsibility are essential. Though there are umpteen workers, each one of them should be made to play a fixed role and should be made responsible for its completion. This is very important in actions involving life and death as in Disaster Management of floods and earthquakes.
- ✓ **Setting Interim Targets and Adopting Scientific Methods of Constant Monitoring Including an Effective Management System (MIS):** Government projects should have an effective management information system. By this they can share and monitor information through mobile phone applications. These can be used to update inspection of roads, bridges and thus help reduce corruption and improve response time by authorities.
- ✓ **Getting the Implements to Share Values and to Own the Results Rather than Just Work to Rule:** We have to transform a job from the “Leaders’ dream” to the dream of the team”. Groups of individuals can never perform well if they only execute orders from superiors. Every team member should feel that it is his own work and responsibility and complete it with a missionary zeal. Of course we should take the cooperation of the other members of the team. Finally it should appear as “Team Success” and not individual success.
- ✓ **Enabling, Empowering and Encouraging Innovations:** there are no prescribed set rules for executing a policy. Every new policy requires a new set of rules and guidelines. So the members of the implementing team should have freedom to experiment, innovate and implement their own ideas. The man on the spot is better suited to decide what to do in a particular situation than the officer at a distance. So over centralization should give place to reasonable decentralization.
- ✓ **Proactively Seeking Beneficiary Feedback to Ensure Quality:** Projects can be best monitored by considering their outcomes. This can be best known through the reaction of the beneficiaries. So for properly monitoring projects we should have a good beneficiary feedback. We can do this by contacting the beneficiaries through mobile applications and other online and offline sources. Some private Corporate Hospitals and the Department of Railways are proactive in gathering feedback from customers to find out the quality and customer satisfaction of their services.

He also elaborately describes the case of RSBY (Rastriya Swasthya Bima Yojana), the National Health Insurance scheme as an example of overcoming implementation challenges faced by the Organizers.

Implementation challenges are present at all levels and the Policy Organizers have to face them. In his book *Public Policy in India* Rajesh Chakrabarthy gives an instance of clearly overcoming challenges in the improvement of state administration. The CM of AP, Chandrababu Naidu before 2004, CM Narendra Modi of Gujarat during 2002-14 and CM Nitish Kumar of Bihar, during 2005-10 could face these challenges successfully owing to their grit and perseverance- are given as examples of “ Turn arounds” or Major shifts in administrative quality. A few implementation strategies of Nitish Kumar administration which have a few common elements with those of the other successful CMs are mentioned here. This is done to trigger thought on the implementation challenges and possible remedies.

In 2005, Nitish Kumar, CM of Bihar had to face many challenges. The state was in a shambles, a real lawless place with roads, schools and hospitals in total disorder. Within 6 years he had managed to turn it into one of the fastest moving states in the country. The CM adopted many strategies to bring about the transformation. The main strategy was that of empowerment with monitoring. The top and middle bureaucracies were given a free hand and a lot of funds to solve the problems. At the same time the CM did not lose touch with the people. He maintained a close touch with them and continued monitoring. He made the officers to report to him regularly. Every month, every fortnight he held review sessions of each department and exerted great pressure on them. Yet he inspired them and succeeded in instilling an extremely demanding work culture in them. Thus he altered not only the functioning of the Bihar government but also solved the issue of corrupt Ministers and Officers. At the same time he maintained direct touch with the masses through his weekly Janatha Darbars and multiple yatras and thus he made them his eyes and ears. Thus he succeeded in transforming Bihar by divorcing administration from electoral politics.

Policies are usually made out of public clamour and the belief that these are solutions to existing problems, but they may not work always. The author also quotes the case of Odd Even Rule of Vehicular Rationing in Delhi to reduce pollution by to some extent. So Policy evaluation is very important, it is the process by which policy framers get feedback for better policy formulation. The impact of the policy is measured in terms of analyses of change before and after the introduction of the policy. It can be evaluated comprehensively by paying due attention to the overall benefits of the policy.

Third Party Evaluation is to be carried out for each of the policy. RCT or Randomized control trials are the Gold Standard in impact evaluation. But it is not always possible to carry it out. Another technique is the difference – in-differencemethod by comparing the beforeand after change or difference. There are also many statistical methods of evaluation but not all evaluation is purely quantitative. Here is a quotation from the prologue of the book *Public Policy in India* by Rajesh Chakrabarthy and Koushiki Sanyal “Public Policy is a matter of life and death of people, societies and even the entire world. It determines the quality of ordinary citizens life, the prosperity of nations, peace, security and sustainability at a geo- political level..... Some say it is much like fixing an airplane in flight”

This is an era of Globalization and we can't escape it. “This means mobility of capital across borders while labour remains stuck to its country of origin. China grew by attracting FDI and this was possible because of its abundant cheap labour. This may be difficult in democratic India”. It is clear that Globalization leads to the interchange of economic, social, cultural, political and technological attributes between societies. But this Globalization has many drawbacks which are very difficult to deal with. It is the duty of the Government to realize this and act as a moderating force to enhance its capacity for policy formulation and implementation. The Indian Government is intelligent and democratic and is based on popular consensus and so it can strike a balance between the short term and long term goals. It has to enhance its transparency by eradicating corruption in public places. Then it can tackle many public issues like the Triple Talaq, Fair Elections, Justice for all and the Elevation of the oppressed and the depressed masses.

It is not always easy to implement policies successfully. Available data speaks of certain failures. Let us consider the data and findings supplied by ASER (Annual Status of Education Report) brought out by the education NGO, Pratham. In 2014 there was 96% school enrollment and yet half of the standard 5th students could not read a simple standard second text. About 40% of students in standard 2nd and 3rd could not recognize numbers up to 100. This low level of children's learning speaks volumes of the policy failure and a report came from a private agency. ASER has now established itself as the nations' trusted benchmark in assessing the degree of effectiveness in Primary education. No wonder this has forced the State Governments to take remedial policy action.

The Government does not accept the new policies easily. When a policy is presented for consideration, the Ministers and Officers want to know if it has precedence, whether it has been found implementable earlier. The policy advocacy groups like the IGC (International Growth Centre, London School of Economics) step in here and suggest new policy ideas to Ministers and Bureaucrats. The Government is receptive to these groups when they come with funding. The Government has come around to accept the superiority of the private sector in the management of large initiatives. They are even ready to forge partnerships with them if their programs are self funded.

“Yet we need significant capital investment to create enterprises, to generate growth and jobs and global investors are a key source. Even Indian investors now have a choice to export their capital if the country’s policies are not favourable. This imposes a set of rules to participate in the global economy, irrespective of the domestic demands and this, in Tom Friedman’s words is called Golden Straitjacket. This is a tight rope that policy makers have to walk carefully, but exit is not an option. So managing the global pressures while serving the interests of the Indian citizens will continue to be a key challenge for the Indian Policy makers”.

In the words of Bhagvan Satya Sai Baba, “No one can conceive of the Almighty without picturing it as Power, Light, Mercy, Wisdom, Energy, Intelligence and Purity. And these qualities can enter the consciousness only through some concrete expressions as the Sun, the Lotus, The Sky, the Ocean and the Wave etc...” In the same way, our country is the Almighty or Bharathmatha. It has all these attributes and the common man should be made to experience these Divine qualities by dedicating and directing all human activity for uplifting the “Daridra- Narayana” through the formulation and implementation of public policies which can pave the way to everlasting peace and contentment.

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